

The Significance Effect of Coffee Quality Practices on Sustainable Export Performance the Mediating Role of Coffee Processing Performance: In Case of Oromia Regional State, West Guji Zone

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Abstract – *The purpose of this study aims the effect of Coffee Quality practice on sustainable Export performance, the Meditating Role of Coffee processing performance; the case of Oromia regional state west Guji Zone. The general aim of this study is to confirm the significance effect of Coffee Quality practice on the Sustainable of Export Performance seeks to understand Export performance process that expressed and latent needs and develop superior solutions for those needs. The research idea stems from study findings that Coffee Quality practice not only affects the Sustainable Export performance of the concern directly but also indirectly Coffee processing performance affect that also confounding to affect directly and indirectly. On the basis and types of data gathered and the instrument used, quantitative research design to use Confirmatory factor analyze and the data analysis were employed for unknown sample size determination valid 384 respondents and as most of the respondent replied to major effect of Coffee Quality practice data have been collected from population of west Guji Zone to use sample from Primary Cooperative union, Secondary Cooperative Union, Coffee Collector, Exporter and ECX and Coffee Traders From Oromia regional state west Guji zone Ethiopia. The scales have been purified and validated with the help of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and the results of structure equation modeling (SEM) revealed a significant relationship*

between Coffee quality practice and sustainable export performance, with mediating role of Coffee processing performance have been confirmed, which yielded to the significant results to used SPSS Version 22 and AMOS 23 to analysis SEM, Standard Regression Weights and model fit value.

Keywords: Coffee Quality practice, Sustainable Export performance, Coffee processing performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the dominant sector in the Ethiopian economy, and the predominant role of coffee Arabica in Ethiopian economic, social and cultural dimensions update to back to several centuries as the country is the primary center of origin and genetic diversity of the plant. According to history, Ethiopia is the world's oldest exporter of coffee that predates 1830 (EU, 2018). Currently, among the top three agricultural export commodities, coffee stands first followed by oilseeds and pulses. The significance of coffee in the Ethiopian economy is enormous and it accounts from 29–31% of coffee export earnings of the nation, 4.7 million (EIAR, 2017).

From the current undertaking of the Marketing of coffee in Ethiopia, it has inferred that the marketer that trades a coffee has highly occupied with routine works. As per the coffee processing had replied, Modern coffee marketing has a complex practice that involves the Production of quality and standard products, the establishment of various and

efficient distribution networks, popularizing the product with fair prices and delivering continuous services after distribution. In this connection the capability of company to compete in the export international market has becoming difficult due to the structure of the production company it has high member of the employee not enable the company to have cost advantage, and the complex Marketing challenge and limited access to market information, Moderate Market Development, Access to Lack of Grading and Storage and Less Transport Facility, (Birhanu et, al, 2015).

(Abiy & Tamene, 2018), and in the competitive international coffee market, the quality of coffee management practice is the main factor to get the achievement of coffee market of Exporters of Coffee. If they can't able to deliver quality coffee practice to their member of Cooperatives, customers or buyers, traders, exporters they will lose their work achievement. Eventually, these situations have tendency to harm country's economy, create loses of foreign exchange and country's revenue has to be highly decreased, and in this situation need more focus and additional study to explore and analyze the existing situation and these initiates to motivate me to analyze the impact of coffee quality practice on its sustainable export performance and contribution to the development, and for the growth of Economy that has launched at national level to contribute the market Efficiency to international market.

So those researchers did not mention this in detail about what can be affected specifically Coffee quality practice on sustainable Export performance among countries, perhaps especially in Ethiopia. So, this is the reason why this study aimed and tried to examine Coffee Quality practice that affected Sustainable Export Performance the Mediating role of Coffee processing Performance, and additionally the overall success was depending on the knowledge of what factors constrain coffee Quality practice and sustainable export performance on the economic growth of the Ethiopian country and these gaps caught the attention of the researcher to do

further study have in the area of export the coffee to develop economic growth relation in the to upgrade the market of Coffee from local market to export the coffee to international market (Birhanu et.al, 2017).

However, the Coffee Quality practice to sustain the Export performance in Oromia Regional state west Guji zone Coffee resource area of six Selected Woredas, like Kercha woreda, Bule Hora woreda, Hambala Wamana woreda, Birbira Kojowa woreda, Galana woreda, and Abaya woreda of Ethiopia has high resourced coffee production and the Coffee processing performance to the contribution of Sustainable Export performance to international marketing has a significance of good national product profitability to achieve market efficiency and to expand market of the national economy and its significant influence level of Coffee quality practice, in Oromia regional state west Guji zone, Ethiopia.

2. OBJECTIVES OF INVESTIGATION

- To analyze the significant effect association among Coffee Quality practice and Sustainable Export performance.
- To describe significant influence association among Coffee Quality practice and Coffee processing performance to confirm significant relationship association among Coffee Quality practice and Sustainable Export performance.

3. COFFEE QUALITY

(Agwanda et al., 2013), globally, quality is the main determinant of coffee consumption of coffee quality as the ability of a set of natural features of product, system or process to meet requirements of the customer's interest. These inherent characteristics can be called "attributes." That regarding coffee each end-user's country that its own organoleptic qualities at different level, at the consumer level, coffee quality deals with price, taste and flavor, effects on health and alertness, geographical origin, environmental and sociological aspects: organic

coffee, fair trade, etc. Coffee has only one value to give the consumer pleasure and satisfaction through flavor, aroma and desirable physiological and psychological effects, (Leroy et al., 2016).

4. COFFEE PROCESSING

(Gada gizachew W., 2021), the effect of Coffee Quality on export performance of Coffee processing involves transforming the coffee cherry into green coffee beans after removing the fruit or pulp and in Ethiopia coffee can produce in both dry coffee processing, wet Coffee processing and Semi washed coffee and while most of the coffee produced prior to the establishment of the Ethiopian Commodity Exchange was to be the unwashed (estimated at approximately 10% of the total production volume), the wet processing gained significance after the establishment of the ECX and it subsequently, its share in volumes processed has gradually increased and currently accounts for 30% of the coffee production (Minten et al., 2016), and for wet coffee to do so it will affect the ultimate coffee quality.

Firstly, the harvested cherries pass through a pulping machine where the skin and pulp are separated. Processing the berries should be collected when they are fully ripe, which enables the coffee to retain a proper fragrance and smoothness (Kufa N., 2018). Once they turn bright red, the berries are picked at intervals of two to three days, and it implies that cherry picking is a rather laborious task. Hereafter, the collected coffee should be taken to and processed at the washing stations within the same day of picking. Failure to do so from the bean and the outer cover of the fruit is washed away, discarding the parchment coffee covered in sticky mucilage (Alemu N., 2018).

5. DRY PROCESSING

Thompson Own 2022, this is known as the natural process or unwashed processing, the newly harvested cherries are sorted then purified out in drying beds for a natural sun drying process, to

guarantee even dryness throughout, the cherries are spread evenly and they are raked multiple times throughout the day, and this process is to take four to six weeks to ensure any excess moisture is completely gone and coffee of dry-processing of coffee can also be wildly inconsistent, and if you want a cleanly fruited, sweet, intense cup, dry process takes more hand labor than the wet process and even the most careful pickers will take green unripe or semi-ripe coffee in the farm to dry processing coffee drying as they pick red, ripe cherry, and if these are not removed in the first days of drying, the green turns to brown that is hard to distinguish from the ripe fruit.

Source: From website 2022

Fig -1: Dry Coffee processing

6. WET PROCESSING COFFEE

(Thompson Own, 2022), wet Specialty coffee is processed using various methods from one origin to other origin, and processed where the bean of the cherry is extracted from the pulp, dried and prepared for exportation, and artisan coffee bean roasting, and explain the wet processing method of coffee in simple terms, using photos from our time spent on the farm of coffee and the method is wet coffee processing, because water is the primary means to both moving the coffee through the process, and to making the extraction of the seed possible and the coffee processing method affects the taste. Understanding these things is important if we are to fully understand why certain coffee

through process to taste the way they do through coffee processing time.

Source: From website 2022

Fig -2: Wet processing Coffee

7. SEMI – WASHED COFFEE

(Jori korohen 2021) Semi washed coffee is a coffee product made from the honey or wet-hull method, in this technique, the outer skin is removed by machines, much like washed coffee, but the mucilage (inner-monocarp), is left on the parchment and sun-dried to be fermented. The parchment is then removed the second drying step begins with the inflated white beans. The coffee turns dark green at 10% to 12% of moisture content, resembling semi washed coffee and it depending on the duration of the drying process, and it will produce the corresponding colors from yellow, red, and black, and this processing technique, which is typical in Brazilian, Indonesian, and Vietnamese coffees, boosts the body and intensity of the coffee the phrase “honey processing” leads many people to assume that the honey used to make coffee or the coffee itself tastes like honey but in reality, that is not the case.

Source: From website 2022

Fig -3: Semi- Washed Coffee

8. SUSTAINABLE EXPORT PERFORMANCE

(Leonidou et al., 2019), the sustainable export performance, as the result of a not only Coffee production and producing actions in commodity of any sustainable export that can be performed markets and it can be considered as an important road map for any company who wishes to review its level of success in terms of export performance of market and sustainable Export performance measures can be classified into objective and subjective measures, the Objective measures are mainly based on the absolute values, while subjective measures are based on perceptual or attitudinal performance. Since it's difficult to clearly segregate export performance results from organizational respondent's results, and it has been deemed advisable to use subjective measures and, in the study, Export performance has measured by using both objective and subjective measures (self-evaluation by respondents), and Subjective sustainable export performance indicators to be measured by the respondent's opinion were based on export sales volume of commodity. (Fantaye & nigussie, 2020).

9. INVESTIGATION GAP

Usually, following revising diverse publications, it has noted that (Lubbadeh, 2021), The over the many research journal and investigation credentials have the many problems gap in statement of the problem and problem statement to derive time, (Lesneer, 2019) the challenge in the process of Coffee Quality Practice and unravel to investigate in Ethiopian Commodity Exchange has to fill the problem gaps of Coffee Quality practice and Sustainable Export Performance. The association to investigation Coffee Quality practice predictor in the worth research parameters of technique logical vacuum of theoretical and empirical gap with citation problem and copy pasts in many research paradigms (Strah & Rupp, 2020), the Investigation research approach qualitative, quantitative, and Mixed research design to confirm build the model, Information analyze and Interpretation based on the output of data (Pereira et. al., 2021), and Sampling

technique strategy for population category of homogeneity and heterogeneity was face challenge to give good reason for sample size determination for large data sample size fill small sample size in study time, deficit of the methodological philosophy gap based on the theory or research approach, and to analyze and interpreted each problem, (Gurhier et al., 2020) and it deficit of Information Source, and Collection Techniques, deficit of data analyze and interpreting ability and finally, defecating factors that affect influencing Coffee Quality practice and Sustainable Export Performance and the process Exploratory factor analyze (EFA) predicator investigation not fit Thus, investigation of Coffee Quality practice has put forward to solve these research gaps (Waithanji& Wakaba, 2014), and Thus, study will have solved the problem of the Coffee Quality practice on Export Performance to rise to fill these gaps.

10. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Source: Amos Structural Equation Model Framework

Fig -4: Conceptual framework

Hypotheses

On the foundation of reviewed literature the researchers framed the below four alternative hypotheses.

H1a: There is statistically significant effect association among Coffee Quality practice and Sustainable Export performance.

H2a: There is statistically significant influence association among Coffee Quality practice and Coffee processing performance.

H3a: There is statistically significant relationship association among Coffee Quality practice and Sustainable Export performance.

11. INVESTIGATION TECHNOLOGY

The study shows the Quantitative research paradigms and it is predicted and data Explain with descriptive, Confirmatory research design and the investigation will be designed by Measurement model of Confirmatory factor analyze predicator Model fit indexes, to measure Validate Convergent validity of AVE, with internal consistency of Discriminant reliability of Composite reliability, Correlation Matrix, Regression weight Model in Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), (Creswell 2003, cited in Isaq, 2019). Therefore, in the investigation, the study will be designed Confirmatory factor analyses to develop the model investigation design and predicator investigation has to be employed to confirm the model characteristics of the phenomena to use for the methods of data analyze, with AMOS V23 software and SPSS Software V.22.

12. SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Simple random sample for each member of population from west Guji zone Primary Cooperative union, Secondary Cooperative Union, Coffee Collector, Exporter and ECX and Coffee Traders From Oromia regional state west Guji zone Coffee resource area of six Selected woreda Kercha woreda, Bule Hora woreda, Hambala Wamana woreda, Birbira Kojowa woreda, Galana woreda and Abaya woreda of Ethiopia has an equal chance of assortment and the ways that are the chance be selected and Stratified random sampling technique, from Primary Cooperative union, Secondary Cooperative Union, Coffee Collector, Exporter and ECX and Coffee Traders are participated to collect the data to the validation of this study.

Suppose we want to calculate a sample size of a large population whose degree of variability is not known. Assuming the maximum variability, N-total population number, which is equal to 50% (p =0.5) and taking 95% confidence level with ±5% precision, the calculation for required sample size will be at infinite or 'N' unknown (Kothari, 2004) formula to developed and calculated a representative developed sample for proportions (Cochrane, 2013).

$$n = \frac{z^2pq}{1+N(e)^2} \quad n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = 384$$

13. VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

Test The research instrument designed in this study - before being distributed to 20 respondents was first tested for the validity and appropriateness of each statement item made in the instrument. For this reason, at this stage, pilot test questionnaires were distributed to 20 respondents, in this case, from Primary Cooperative union, Secondary Cooperative Union, Coffee Collector, Exporter and ECX and Coffee Traders From Oromia regional state west Guji zone Ethiopia that used that public banks the results of the validity and reliability test of the research instruments in this study obtained that the entire statement items were valid and reliable to be used for the next test.

14. CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSES (CFA) MEASUREMENT MODEL

Source: Confirmatory factor analysis (2022)

Fig -5: Confirmatory Factor analysis Measurement Model

15. COVARIANCE MATRIX

Table -1: Covariance: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
COPPE	<-->	SEPE	.321	.050	6.403	***	par_36
COQAU	<-->	SEPE	.283	.044	5.405	***	par_37
COQAU	<-->	COPPE	.565	.074	7.627	***	par_38

Source: Composite Reliability 2022

Covariance matrix a square matrix that displays the variance matrix exhibited by elements of datasets and the covariance between Coffee Quality practice Coffee processing performance and Sustainable Export Performance of C.R value is 6.403, Coffee processing performance with Sustainable Export Performance C.R Value 5.403 and Coffee Quality practice and Coffee processing performance7.627, and the pair of datasets with Significance p-value 0.000 and the Variance measurement model is a measure of dispersion and can be spread of data from the mean of the given dataset and Covariance matrix is calculated between two variables and is used to measure how the two variables vary together is accepted and the measurement model design is fitted.

16. CORRELATION MATRIX

Table -2: Correlations: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate
COPPE	<-->	SEPE	.538
COQAU	<-->	SEPE	.606
COQAU	<-->	COPPE	.912

Source: Composite Reliability 2022

The correlation between the constructed and demonstrated on AMOS static suggested all are meaning full and summarized these number shows the Correlation between the among confirmatory factors analysis in respects to their standard deviation to the study, and the correlation among those factors which helps in confirming measurement model, those the value of Correlation Coefficient value result of all three model has the result more than 0.3 and high and strong correlation coefficient value more than 0.5 and the Alternative Hypothesis has to be Accepted and highly correlated and the Null hypothesis measurement model has to be predicted Rejected or Unsupported based on this reason the Model are highly fitted.

17. MODEL FIT SUMMARY

Table -3: Model Fit indices for structural model

NO	Index	Criterion	Final over all model
01	Chi-square χ^2	Low	1.157
02	Df	< 3	.162
03	(P- value)	≤ .05	.000
04	Normed chi-square	< 20	187.373
05	Goodness off it index(GFI)	> .90	.955
06	Adjusted goodness off it index (AGFI)	> .90	.930
07	Normed fit index (NFI)	> .90	.944
08	Relative fit index(RFI)	> .90	.920
09	Incremental fit index (IFI)	>.90	.992
10	Tucker kiwis index (TLI)	>.95	.988
11	Comparative fit index (CFI)	>.95	.992
12	Root Mean Square error (RMR)	≤ .05	.152
13	Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	≤ .05	.021

Source: Composite Reliability, 2022

The Model Fit Summary Value showed, Chi-square (Chi-square χ^2) direct effect the result to 1.157, Df (Degree of Freedom) result shows .162 will Normed chi-square value 187.373 with a significant P-value is .000, and a CFI value of .992 as (RMR) value has value.152, GFI Results .955, AGFI value results .930, NFI

value result .944, Relative fit index(RFI) result .920 along with the (RMSEA) value of .021 and Exogenous variable Coffee Quality practice, Confounding or Mediating variable of Coffee processing performance and Sustainable Export performance result, it which implies that the null H0 hypothesis based on the science estimation is rejected, as well the alternative Ha1 is highly accepted (Hair et al, 2010).

18. DISCRIMINANT RELIABILITY AND CONVERGENT VALIDITY TESTS

Table -4: Standardized Regression Weights: Cronbach Alpha, Composite reliability and Convergent reliability test results

Indicator variable	Loading		Latent Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE% >.50
COQUA1	.735	<---	Coffee Quality Practice	.787	.780	.620
COQUA2	.643	<---				
COQUA3	.725	<---				
COQUA4	.619	<---				
COQUA5	.705	<---				
COQUA6	.658	<---				
COPPE1	.559	<---	Coffee Processing Performance	.860	.850	.610
COPPE2	.668	<---				
COPPE3	.576	<---				
CUPPE4	.653	<---				
CUPPE5	.660	<---				
CUPPE6	.711	<---				
SEPE1	.918	<---	Sustainable Export Performance	.820	.823	.622
SEPE2	.680	<---				
SEPE3	.736	<---				
SEPE4	.713	<---				
SEPE5	.687	<---				

Source: Cronbach Alpha, Composite Reliability and AVE result 2022

The Internal Consistency of Discriminant Reliability (Composite Reliability), Cronbach alpha value and Convergent validity is obtained when the AVE% value is greater than 0.5% (Hair et al., 2010), and the AVE% results of convergent validity to constructs of Coffee Quality practice model is in AVE>740 indicate that the Construct Validity test is satisfied. Composite Reliability tests are more than >0.6% are also accepted when internal reliability of composite reliability it means Coffee Quality Practice value result is .780 Coffee processing performance result .850 and Sustainable Export performance result .823 and all Cronbach alpha value are > 0.7% it implies result of CR (composite reliability) is accepted when all constructs show a CR value greater than 0.60, Average extracted variance all (AVE) result has also >0.5% has to be accepted and Cronbach alpha value are > 0.7% because all sub-constructs showed the results of confirmatory factor analysis of value fit indices result is highly accepted and supported (Zainuddin, 2022).

19. STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING (ESM)

In this procedure again model fits would be testified, but the effect among the construct has to be considered for making the different between confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling based on the SEM model demonstrated the Central and non-central indices based the regression weight and the model to be tasted is represented in figure 6.

Source: Results of Structural Equation Modeling Direct hypotheses (2022)

Fig -6:The overall Structural Equation Modeling Coffee quality practice and sustainable Export performance.

20. REGRESSION WEIGHTS

Table -5: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
COPPE	<---	COQAU	1.160	.140	8.304	***	par_36
EPE	<---	COQAU	.654	.325	2.009	***	par_37
EPE	<---	COPPE	-.061	.243	.253	.040	par_38
COQUA1	<---	COQAU	1.000				
COQUA2	<---	COQAU	.819	.093	8.834	***	par_1
COQUA3	<---	COQAU	.977	.120	8.129	***	par_2
COQUA4	<---	COQAU	1.064	.120	8.875	***	par_3
COQUA5	<---	COQAU	1.066	.119	8.946	***	par_4
COQUA6	<---	COQAU	.719	.107	6.720	***	par_5
COPPE1	<---	COPPE	1.000				
COPPE2	<---	COPPE	1.000	.085	11.757	***	par_6
COPPE3	<---	COPPE	.426	.071	5.982	***	par_7
CUPPE4	<---	COPPE	.465	.073	6.351	***	par_8
CUPPE5	<---	COPPE	.401	.075	5.354	***	par_9
CUPPE6	<---	COPPE	.586	.080	7.357	***	par_10
SEPE 1	<---	SEPE	1.000				
SEPE2	<---	SEPE	1.290	.113	11.434	***	par_11
SEPE3	<---	SEPE	1.223	.104	11.708	***	par_12

Source: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model, 2022).

The Standardized Regression Weights suppose we have a network with a path connecting from latent variable and measurement variables, that means from Measurement model and structural model value of standardized path coefficient beta is highly affected, and it can be expected to increase by one

standardized deviation (error) that means that predicted variables from its own mean while holding, all the other relevant variables is constant and Coffee quality practice, Coffee processing performance, Sustainable export Performance and other indicted variables has goes up by 1 standard deviation that goes More than 0.6 standard deviations and the Standardized coefficient value regression weight is very well and the standardize regression weight group results have highly affected and solve the problem Banks of their commercial Banks of Main bank, Bariso Dukale and Goro Dugda Bule Hora town Ethiopia.

21. HYPOTHESES TEST RESULTS

Table –6: Standard Regression Weights hypothesis

No	Indigenous Variable		Exogenous Variables	C.R	P	Conclusion
01	COPPE	<---	COQP	8.304	***	Accepted
02	SEPE	<---	COQP	2.009	***	Accepted
03	SEPE	<---	COPPE	.253	.040	Accepted

Source: Output of Hypothesis testing (2022)

Hypothesis testing is done with (Coffee Quality practice Coffee with Coffee Processing performance C.R Value 8.304, Coffee Processing performance with Sustainable Export Performance C.R value 2.009 and Coffee Processing performance with Sustainable Export performance value .253), with three hypothesis result less than the 0.05 using the t-count that estimate by SEM in AMOS V. 23 software, the t-count is the critical ratio (CR) value for weight regression, and the (CR) value is greater than 1.967 that means (Coffee Quality practice or the likelihood with all P-value result is < 0.05, then H0 Null hypothesis can be rejected, and the alternative p-value estimation can be Accepted < 0.05, which Means the data has implies that accepted the hypothesis of the results of hypothesis testing in this study.

22. CONCLUSION

Covariance matrix a square matrix that displays the variance matrix exhibited by elements of datasets and the covariance between Coffee Quality practice Coffee processing performance and Sustainable Export Performance of C.R value is 6.403, Coffee processing performance with Sustainable Export Performance C.R Value 5.403 and Coffee Quality practice and Coffee processing performance 7.627, and the pair of datasets with Significance p-value 0.000 and the Variance measurement model is a measure of dispersion and can be spread of data from the mean of the given dataset and Covariance matrix is calculated between two variables and is used to measure how the two variables vary together is accepted and the measurement model design is fitted.

The correlation between the constructed and demonstrated on AMOS static suggested all are meaning full and summarized these number shows the Correlation between the among confirmatory factors analysis in respects to their standard deviation to the study, and the correlation among those factors which helps in confirming measurement model, those the value of Correlation Coefficient value result of all three model has the result more than 0.3 and high and strong correlation coefficient value more than 0.5 and the Alternative Hypothesis has to be Accepted and highly correlated and the Null hypothesis measurement model has to be predicted Rejected or Unsupported based on this reason the Model are highly fitted.

The Model Fit Summary Value showed, Chi-square (Chi-square χ^2) direct effect the result to 1.157, Df (Degree of Freedom) result shows .162 normal chi-square value 187.373 with a significant P-value is .000, and a CFI value of .992 as (RMR) value has value .152, GFI Results .955, AGFI value results .930, NFI value result .944, Relative fit index (RFI) result .920 along with the (RMSEA) value of .021 and Exogenous variable Coffee Quality practice, Confounding or Mediating variable of Coffee processing performance and Sustainable Export performance

result, it which implies that the null H0 hypothesis based on the science estimation is rejected, as well the alternative Ha1 is highly accepted (Hair et al, 2010).

The Internal Consistency of Discriminant Reliability (Composite Reliability), Cronbach alpha value and Convergent validity is obtained when the AVE% value is greater than 0.5% (Hair et al., 2010), and the AVE% results of convergent validity to constructs of Coffee Quality practice model is in AVE>740 indicate that the Construct Validity test is satisfied. Composite Reliability tests are more than >0.6% are also accepted when internal reliability of composite reliability it means Coffee Quality Practice value result is .780 Coffee processing performance result .850 and Sustainable Export performance result .823 and all Cronbach alpha value are > 0.7% it implies result of CR (composite reliability) is accepted when all constructs show a CR value greater than 0.60, Average extracted variance all (AVE) result has also >0.5% has to be accepted and Cronbach alpha value are > 0.7% because all sub-constructs showed the results of confirmatory factor analysis of value fit indices result is highly accepted and supported (Zainuddin, 2022).

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